

INDIGOFERA TINCTORIA L. AS A PROSPECTIVE PLANT

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Great attention is being paid to the study of promising plants for the national economy of our republic, their involvement in production, cultivation and propagation in different regions. One such promising dye plant is *Indigofera tinctoria* L. species.

Indigofera tinctoria This miraculous plant has been widely used in several ways for a long time. In agriculture, it helps to increase the productivity of the land and is a source of nitrogen for sugarcane crops, fruit trees, tea and coffee plantations and vineyards. In Tibetan and Indo-Chinese folk medicine, it is especially valued as an antibacterial and antifungal agent in the pharmaceutical industry.

The leaves of *Indigofera tinctoria* are also widely used in medicine. The plant contains indirubin, rathenoid deguelin, legidrodegulin, rotenol, teforsin and sumatrol. Its root and plant leaves are used in medicine [2].

The plant *Indigofera tinctoria* is used in the treatment of various skin diseases, boils, eczema, sore throat, laryngitis, gum inflammation and sore throat, in the treatment of cancer and leukemia and liver diseases, and also in the treatment of dog bites or snake bites. In addition.

Anti-inflammatory properties of *Indigofera tinctoria* in cosmetology relieves itching, heals inflammation and soothes the itchy scalp, protects the scalp with an antiseptic, cleanses, eliminates dandruff, helps hair to be soft, soft, and voluminous[1,3].

Henna and basma are the only natural hair dyes. *Indigofera* strengthens hair roots and improves their structure, nourishes hair, ensures their proper growth and creates a protective shell.

Indigofera tinctoria L. The plant is also used to restore the soil of polluted lands, to obtain a valuable natural dye, as a nitrogen-rich fertilizer, to improve the soil ecology, in medicine, as a medicine, and as an antidepressant [1].

In conclusion, it can be said that the process of obtaining dye from *Indigofera tinctoria* is cheap and, importantly, harmless to human health. The useful aspect of the plant for the textile industry is that it can be a necessary raw material [3].

Based on these, it is possible to grow *Indigofera tinctoria* in different regions of our republic. *Indigofera tinctoria* can also be grown in areas with reduced soil

fertility. Secondly, the natural dye obtained from the leaves of this plant can be effectively used in textile and light industrial enterprises of our republic.

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